

A proposal for a modeling methodology based on a smart irrigation use case

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1. Process modeling methodology

The goal of the preliminary models presented in this document is to describe, through an example, the methodology for process modeling to be used in T3.3.

The modeling activity can be evaluated from multiple perspectives. From a technical perspective, it consists in the use of formal languages from software engineering to represent processes and transformation of processes after the introduction of digital technology in a given context. From an interdisciplinary point of view, it allows creating a picture of the system of interest for all the stakeholders to be involved, from the business owners to external experts and academia. Once completed, the model will provide qualitative hints to carry out the cost-benefit analysis through a description of the digital components in the Living Lab (ecosystem under consideration), the actors and interactions therein, further that communication, exploitation, and likely demonstration activities. The modeling activity will require a few iterations, guided by CNR, among actors and Living Lab coordinators.

In this example, input data for the modeling (text in section 2) were provided by UNIPI after visiting a farm and interviewing the actors involved (business owner and agronomist). On such basis, CNR developed a model (diagrams in section 3) of the process, actors, and goals, aiming at highlighting how the system changed after the introduction of digital technology (e.g., irrigation). In this example, there were no iterations following the visit to the farm, which left a few questions unanswered. Those are the ones we refer to as “triggered questions”, presented below each model, as an example of questions that may arise after the first development of the model. In CODECS, however, we expect Living Labs to carry out the modeling according to the guidelines with minimal interactions with the task leader.

A key requirement for the project is the understandability of the models, implying that all the elements used for modeling are well explained and clear to all stakeholders.

The figure presents the modeling workflow described above.

The methodology will likely be adapted in CODECS to accommodate multiple needs. For instance, a subset of living labs will be modeled adopting the complete workflow (e.g., those more familiar with the methodology and considering the use of “advanced” technology); other living labs, on a case-by-case basis, may follow a lighter version of the methodology. Data will be

collected in a structured way and will represent the basis to deliver process models. Training sessions will be organized and guidelines to be followed will be provided.

A second case study is under preliminary analysis with the purpose of refining and testing the methodology. The CODECS living lab based in Tuscany is providing support on this activity in this preliminary phase.

INPUT DATA. THE REPORT BY UNIFI

2. Understanding Irrigation system Innovation

Introduction

Water is one of the major resources used in agriculture. Agricultural activities including livestock and crop production consumes a large quantity of water. Globally, irrigation consumes about 70% of freshwater. Due to climate change resulting in temperature rise and variation in the rainfall pattern, and population increase, there is an upsurge in the use of water for agricultural production. Thus, a growing concern for water conservation has called for innovations to sustain irrigation, meeting the needs of the farmers, and ensuring environmental quality. A wireless sensor network (WSN) and the precision irrigation management protocol were transferred to illuminati frutta consortium company located at Arezzo in Italy. The sensor was designed and validated in two planting seasons 2019-2020. The total area of the farmland is 350ha with apples, pears, peaches, and plums cultivated in it, but the smart irrigation strategy was applied in the pear orchard of about 7ha. The WSN measures the soil moisture and evapotranspiration of the crop and with the precision irrigation management protocol, there is a promising potential of economic, productive, and environmental benefits. Economic; resource use

efficiency saving up to 50% of the total water supplied with ordinary irrigation management and reduced irrigation duration to 3 hours per single watering, Productive; improvement in the quality and quantity of harvest, Environmental; sustainable land management and protection against groundwater contamination by wastewater. we adopt a broad approach to understand how innovations come up.

A multi-level perspective to irrigation system innovation.

Technological development starts from the birth of an idea to a point where the technology is commercially exploited. The development stage is a learning phase, the technology does not have its rules articulated and its network consists of very few elements. Technological innovations breed several related elements linked together in a working configuration. These elements do not function on their own without the involvement of human actors. Overtime, adjustment, and improvement done are determined by the societal elements such as user preference, policies, legislation, and institutional settings. It involves a change from one socio-technical system to another. I will explain how transition to a new irrigation system innovation takes place using the 3 concepts of multi- level perspective.

1. **Socio-technical regimes:** The regime is defined by the technology, societal element, and the rule set. The technology is embedded in the society while the rule set is embedded in the technological and societal element.

Figure 1. Representation of a socio-technical regime.

In the irrigation system, we have identified some elements as described in Fig 2, these elements cannot function without the human actors that form the social groups e.g., research network (university and technical institute), public authorities, users, producer network, farmers manufacturers, suppliers etc. Although these social groups have a distinctive feature and rules in their own environment, they are interdependent and interact with each other, therefore forming a wider category of rules in the system. The rules provide stability by guiding the perceptions and actions of actors.

Irrigation procedure in the farm before the introduction of the technology.

The new technology builds on the existing regime. For the ordinary irrigation management, the farmer irrigates the farm in a fixed shifts of 2-3 days and between 6-7 hours. We have the sprinkler and superficial drip irrigation method installed in the farm. The drippers are used directly on the crops while the sprinklers are used when there are abnormal periods of high or low ambient temperature. The water source for the irrigation process is the Montedoglio dam hydrant and alternatively, from the company well.

- **What are the drivers of change in regime?**
- **What are the costs and benefits of moving from the regime to the niche?**

Figure 2. Illustration of the socio-technical irrigation system.

2. **Technological niches:** Just like we often say, “carve a niche for yourself”, niches are protected and with a unique responsibility. At this level invention supersedes and tend to replace an existing technology because niches are created to solve the problems that exist in the regime or socio-technical landscape that causes instability in the regime (climate change, policies, and regulations). The pilot field experiment in the farm is a

strategic research and development investment, funded and involves range of actors including company, suppliers, university, funding agencies, local and national authority. This is a form of protection that shield the technology from market selection. According to Schot (1998), a niche is like an “incubation room” for radical novelty. In this case study, the term novelty is defined by one generated by putting an existing technology to a new use (irrigation domain). There is uncertainty about the technical design rules, and user preference because there is often rule sets from more than one regime that will affect the niche e.g., energy regime, agricultural regime, and water regime. The niche is an experimentation, a learning process, vision articulation and a space to build the social network that support the technology in the new domain. The performance of the wireless sensor network for irrigation is low based on its consumption and adoption in the farm. This may be attributed to farmers being engrained with the existing regime organizationally, economically, and culturally.

- **What are the contributing factors and the possibility of a breakout from the niche level?**

3. **Socio-technical landscape:** This is the environment that the socio-technical irrigation systems exist on, and they are wider factors that put pressure on the regime. They

stimulate a breakthrough for transition and cannot be influenced by actors in the regime but influences technological development e.g., environmental problem, globalization, policies, population growth.

The wireless sensor network (WSN)

The wireless sensor network used for irrigation detects the soil moisture and the evapotranspiration of the crop (pear). There are interactions between multiple digital tools such as unmanned aerial vehicle (UAV), GIS tools, remote-sensing (satellite) data, drones (hexacopter) with a multispectral camera, and Pix4D Professional photogrammetry software, that converts weather, soil, and crop information technically into digital form. Monitoring the water status of the soil, a predefined optimal range is maintained and if there is need for prevention and immediate correction intervention due to deviation from the optimal condition, the alarm and control system is activated. The feedback control protocol identifies the right time for irrigation intervention following the threshold value of water content of the substrate, and right water quantity required to bring the soil to normalcy. The watering volumes is quantified as a function of rainfall and soil moisture. The farmers get information with the use of an application on their phone.

The optimal use of the WSN network will not be achievable without the data analysis and the decision support system (DSS). A decision support system is an interactive software-based system with a database, model (the decision context and user criteria), and user interface components used for decision making.

Figure 3. The AgriNet Network DSS. Source: (Bonzi, 2020)

The AgriNet DSS includes the drill and drop type of sensor (Sentek Inc) and nodes installed in the farm with the guideline of the manufacturer. It reads the soil moisture, and the data is sent to the server for storage and analysis using a software. The nodes installed in the farm are powered with the solar energy and communicates with the transceiver. Through the serial/ ethernet interface the transceiver sends data to an internet gateway that uses 3G technology and connects to the network of the nearest telephone company. The information is entered into a MYSQL database on the AgriNET (Tuctronics) web platform for analysis.

Figure 4. AgriNet app and information available to the user. Source: (Bonzi, 2020)

3. Process modeling, CNR

The following diagrams aim to represent the innovative irrigation system adopted by Illuminati, giving details of the processes both before and after the introduction of technology, and also taking into account the overall system, actors involved, goals, and relationships. The diagrams are developed using three standard modeling languages UML, i* and BPMN focusing on the representation of different aspects: UML structure diagram describes the classes involved and their relationships, goal model in i* focuses on the goals of the actors and BPMN process diagrams describe the irrigation processes both before and after the introduction of the smart irrigation system.

Below each diagram a list of questions triggered by the modeling activities is provided as an example of the additional information needed to further refine the diagrams. The models proposed cannot be considered exact reproductions of the processes because some information is missing but they can be an example of a common language for information exchange between experts of different domains involved in the adoption and evaluation of technology.

3.1 Structure diagram (UML)

The UML structure diagram provides an overview of the classes, i. e. actors, tools, infrastructures, and systems involved in the precision irrigation system and the relationships between them, i.e., roles and actions performed.

Legend of UML symbols used

Explanation of symbols

Class: defines the core elements. It is represented by a box with a title label on the top (in capital letter) and two inner sections divided by a line. On the upper section there is a list of the attributes that describe the class (i.e. *name*, *password*, *id* for the user of a system); below there is the list of operations exploited by the class, e. g. *login*, *readData*, *startIrrigation*, *stopIrrigation* are all the operations performed by the user of the smart irrigation system. An operation is written with round brackets in the end, like in language programming notation.

Relations: connect classes and are expressed by arrows. Different types of arrows represent different types of associations. In the schema below three types of relations are used (see the legend above for a graphical representation). The first type is direct association, that connects two classes by means of an operation (i. e. *Irrigation tool* class irrigates the field by the *irrigateCrop()* operation, while the *Field* class receives water through *receiveWater()* operation). The arrow is directed towards the passive class that receives the call (e. g. The irrigation tool irrigates the fields with the *irrigateCrop()* operation activating the operation *receiveWater()* of the *Field* class). The second type of relation is composition and it tells that a class is a component of another class (e. g. The *DSS infrastructure* class is composed by the *WSN*, *DSS software* and *Internet gateway* classes). The third type is the generalization which means that the class is based on another upper-level class and inherits all attributes and operations of that class (e. g. *Sprinkler* is a generalization of the class *Irrigation tool*).

Multiplicity is a numerical notation located at both edges of a relation to explain how many classes are involved in the relation. E. g. One or more (1..*) irrigation tools are responsible for the irrigation of one (1) field.

Description of the diagram

The structure diagram contains the class *User* at the top left. The class represents the human agent (the field owner or agronomist who is in charge for the irrigation). The attributes of the *User* are: *id* (an identifier to access the system), *name* and *password*. The operations are *login* and *readData*, used for the connection with *DSS infrastructure* and *startIrrigation* and *stopIrrigation*, used for starting and stopping the irrigation tools. Thus the *User* class has two relations: one with *DSS infrastructure* class and the other with *Irrigation tool* class. The *DSS Infrastructure* class at the top right of the diagram contains a single *id* attribute and the operation *provideIrrigationData* that is activated by the *User* class. Below the *DSS infrastructure* class there are three other related classes: *WSN*, *Internet gateway* and *DSS software*. The composition relation between *DSS infrastructure* and each one of these classes implies that the three classes are components of the upper level class. *WSN* (i.e. Wireless Sensors Network, the sensor network used for measurement) has an attribute *id* and four operations: *connectToNetwork* for connecting to the *Internet gateway*, *measureSoilMoisture* and *measureEvapotranspiration* which connect the class to the *Field* class and *sendDataToDSS* that sends data about measurement to the *DSS software*. *Internet gateway* is another component of the *DSS infrastructure*. It has an *id* attribute and an operation *provideConnectivity* to provide to the other components the Internet connection necessary for exchanging data. *DSS software* is the third component of the infrastructure and it is the software in charge for the storage (*receiveDataFromWSN*, *storeData*) and analysis of measurement data (*analyseData* and *provideData*).

On the bottom left part of the schema there are the classes involved in the irrigation process. From the left to the right there are: *Water source*, that has an attribute *coords* representing the coordinates of the water source and the operation *provideWater* that is activated by the *Irrigation tool* class. *Water source* has three generalization classes (at the bottom) that represent the three types of water source used by Illuminati: the *Well*, the *Dam* and the *River*. *Irrigation tool* class represents the tool used for irrigating the crop and is linked to the *Water source* class (demanding it water), to the *Field* class (to which water is provided) and to the *User*

class, that has the control on the tool activation. The attributes of the *Irrigation tool* class are *id* and *coords*, the latter expressing the location of the tool in the field. The corresponding operations are *start*, *stop*, *receiveWater* and *irrigateCrop*. *Irrigation tool* class has a generalization relation with *Sprinkler* and *Dripper* classes which inherit all its attributes and operations.

The last class of the diagram is *Field* that is related both to *Irrigation tool* from which it receives water (*receiveWater*) and *WSN* from which it is measured (*isMeasured*). The attributes of *Field* class are *coords* and *area* that allow us to locate it and *id* for being managed by the *DSS infrastructure*.

To highlight the fundamental role of digital technologies in the smart irrigation process structure, in the schema above digital technologies classes are in light-blue.

Example question triggered by the UML modeling:

- The tools mentioned in the report: aerial vehicle (UAV), GIS tools, remote-sensing (satellite) data, drones (hexacopter) with a multispectral camera, and Pix4D Professional photogrammetry software are already part of the system? Are they integrated into the DSS? How?

ANSWER: these tools are used to set up the model (e.g. to understand where the sensors have to be placed). An additional structural model with a description of system setup could be useful for installation costs estimation and other evaluations.

3.2 Goal diagram (i*)

The i* (iStar) diagram models the goals of the irrigation process focusing on the intentional (why?), social (who?), and strategic (how? how else?) dimensions. In the schema are highlighted actors, components, activities performed in relation to the goals and qualities.

The schema below focuses on the demonstration of the positive impact of the introduction of the new actor “*DSS infrastructure*” and its measurement activities in supporting the irrigation task performed by the farmer.

Explanation of symbols:

Actor: an active, autonomous entity that aims at achieving its goals by exercising its know-how, in collaboration with other actors;

Actor boundary (represented by a circle): contains all tasks, goals, qualities, resources and dependencies related to a single actor;

Task: represents an action that an actor wants to be executed;

Goal: a state of affairs that the actor wants to achieve;

Quality: an attribute for which an actor desires some level of achievement. Qualities guide the search for ways of achieving goals;

Resource/tool: a physical or informational entity that an actor requires in order to perform a task

Other elements used in the diagram:

Contribution links: the links between a quality and other elements represent the effects of intentional elements on qualities. The effects can be fulfilled (in this case the keyword “*make*” is used for expressing sufficient positive evidence while “*help*” for weak positive evidence) or denied (with “*hurt*” or “*break*”). In the following diagram the *measure soil moisture* task performed by *WSN makes* automation quality achieved.

Dependum: an intentional element that is the object of a dependency. A dependency is a social relationship between two actors (a dependee and a depender). In the following diagram the task “*analyse data*” performed by the *DSS software makes* the quality *data analysis precision* fulfilled and going out from the WSN infrastructure boundary allows the realization of the farmer’s goals “*water saving*” and “*sustainable land management*”.

Description of the diagram

The actors represented in the model are the *Farmer* (on the left) and the *DSS Infrastructure* (on the right). Inside the *Farmer’s boundary*, which is delimited by the blue circle, there are his

goals: *quantity improvement, quality improvement, water saving, and sustainable land management*. The goals are linked to the action below *irrigate field* performed by the farmer through the use of *irrigation tools* and *water* as resource. Each goal is also linked to the quality by a contribution link, i. e. *water saving* goal is linked to the *sustainability* quality through the contribution link *help* that indicates that the quality is fulfilled.

The *DSS Infrastructure* boundary contains the tasks performed linked to the tool adopted: *measure soil moisture* and *measure evapotranspiration* by *WSN*, *provide connectivity* by *Internet gateway* and *storage* and *analyse data* by *DSS software*. The quality *precision* and the task *provide irrigation* are located outside the boundary of *DSS Infrastructure* having the role of dependum between the actor *Farmer* (as the depender) and *DSS Infrastructure* (as the dependee).

Example questions triggered by the I model:*

- Is there any possible correlation between the adoption of the smart irrigation and the quality and quantity improvement goals?

3.3 Process diagrams (BPMN)

The BPMN process diagrams represent the detailed flow of the irrigation process.

The first diagram describes the process before the introduction of technology as reported in section 2. The second describes the precision irrigation system introduced by the DSS infrastructure.

The third is an overlap of the two models to focus on the process reengineering impacts.

Legend of BPMN symbols used

Explanation of symbols

Start event: defines the starting point of a process. It can contain a timer to express a delay or a repetitive process (see **start timer event**) or it can be triggered by another process and contain a message;

End event: defines the ending point of a process;

Task: is an atomic activity within a process flow. It can be of different types. The types of services represented in the following models are: manual, service, send;

Parallel gateway: is used to visualize the concurrent execution of activities;

Exclusive gateway: is used to create alternative paths within a process flow. For a given instance of the process, only one of the paths can be taken;

Intermediate timer event: has a time duration definition that defines when it is triggered;

Pool: A pool represents a participant who takes part in a process. All actions performed by the participant are represented inside the same pool. If multiple participants are involved in a process, multiple pools are defined. Connections between participants are represented with dashed lines.

SCHEMA BPMN 1: irrigation *before* digital technology

Description of the diagram

The schema represents the daily process of irrigation carried out by a single actor (farmer). The process contains two parallel paths expressed with a *parallel gateway*: in the path above the *temperature is checked* and if abnormal temperature is detected the *sprinkle irrigation is started*, otherwise the *process ends*. The path below describes the *parallel task of drip irrigation* scheduled every three days: every day the process controls if is irrigation day accessing an external data source like a calendar and if it is irrigation day the *drip irrigation* is started, otherwise the process ends. Both drip and sprinkle irrigation are manual tasks that are executed by the farmer for a limited amount of time expressed by the duration property of the intermediate timer event inserted between the start and the end task. The triggered questions below the diagram emphasize the need to provide the more accurate data (i.e. timer duration or scheduled periods) in order to allow automatic evaluations of the processes.

Example questions triggered by the model:

- Does the process start with a temperature check? How often is it performed? Is it a manual process or does it involve an external service (meteo, website, app)?
- Start / stop sprinklers and start/stop dripper: is this a manual activity?
- What is it intended with 'abnormal temperature'? Is it based on any existing parameter? How is it identified? What is the procedure?
- Is it possible to quantify the duration of the sprinkle irrigation? What does it depend on?
- Is the dripper irrigation (frequency and duration) always constant? Are there any differences between seasons, abnormal climate, etc that may incide on it?

SCHEMA BPMN 2: precision irrigation (after the introduction of the wireless sensors network and of the decision support system)

Description of the diagram

The schema describes the process of irrigation after the introduction of *DSS infrastructure*. The three pools represent the three participants of the process. The pool at the bottom contains the *Wireless Sensors Network* that start with a *start timer event* triggering two parallel activities: *soil moisture measurement* and *evapotranspiration measurement*. The representation of these activities is simplified due to the limited amount of information provided in the text (report in section 3.2) but if further information were provided they could be represented as sub-processes. Information about the frequency of the measurements is currently missing too. The parallel measurement tasks end with a *send task* in which measurement data are sent to the other upper participant *decision support system (DSS)*. *DSS* central pool starts with a *message starting event* containing data sent by the *WSN*. Data are accumulated in the server until an *analysis* task is performed (the flow is controlled by an *exclusive gateway* checking from an external source if is it time to perform the analysis). The aim of the analysis is to detect a *deviation from the optimal condition* of soil moisture and evapotranspiration. An *exclusive gateway* controls the management of the deviation: if it is detected a subsequent message task *sends an alert* to an application that can be accessed by the *user* represented in the upper pool. The *user's pool* starts with the *alert triggered* by the *DSS* that contains important information about *quantity of water needed and time to irrigate*. Depending on the content of the message, passing through an exclusive gateway the farmer decides to *start irrigation (drip or sprinkle)* or *ignore the alert*. All the three options bring to the end of the process.

Example questions triggered by the model:

- Is the regular drip irrigation process scheduled every 2-3 days completely replaced?
- How often the *WSN* sends data to the *DSS*?
- How often the automatic data analysis by *DSS* is performed?
- Are the parameters for the activation of the control system alarms accessible to the user / are they customizable? / are there different user level for accessing the data of the *DSS* (user, admin)? / is it a black-box / are data available?
- Is it possible for the user starting a parallel "manual system check" process to access the data independently from the activation of the control system alarm?
- Has the user any control over the activation/deactivation of the control system alarm?

SCHEMA BPMN 3: an overlap of the two models for comparison

The new participants, activities and gateways introduced by technology are in blue; in green the activities and gateways that do not change; in red the activities and gateways that are not present anymore.

4. FEEDBACK

Please answer the short survey and provide a feedback about the models and overall methodology.

<https://forms.gle/Tjag3MjRmZ9kx5T18>